

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON PUBLIC RELATIONS PRACTICE IN AKWA IBOM STATE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

This study examines the influence of social media on public relations practice at Akwa Ibom State University (AKSU), Nigeria. The research aimed to determine the extent of social media use, identify preferred platforms, and uncover barriers to effective utilisation. We conducted a survey among PR practitioners at AKSU using a quantitative approach. Findings reveal that Facebook is the dominant platform, with 48% of respondents using it for PR activities. The majority of practitioners perceive social media as having a significant influence on their work, enhancing relationship-building and information dissemination. However, infrastructural challenges, primarily, insufficient electricity and poor network connectivity, hinder optimal social media use. The study concludes that while social media plays a crucial role in AKSU's PR practice, addressing infrastructure barriers is essential for maximising its potential. Recommendations include investing in alternative power sources, developing a comprehensive social media strategy, and providing regular training for PR practitioners on emerging trends and best practices.

Keywords: social media, public relations, higher education

Introduction

The advent of social media has revolutionised communication practices across various sectors, including public relations (PR). As organisations strive to maintain effective relationships with their stakeholders, the integration of social media into PR strategies has become increasingly crucial. This study examines the influence of social media on public relations practice at Akwa Ibom State University (AKSU), Nigeria.

In recent years, social media platforms have emerged as powerful tools for information dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and brand management. Bryer and Zavattaro (2011) define social media as technologies that facilitate social interaction, enable collaboration, and foster deliberations across stakeholders. The rise of platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp, and LinkedIn has transformed the communication landscape, offering new opportunities and challenges for PR practitioners.

Public relations, as defined by Asemah (2010), is the process of creating awareness about an organisation's policies, programs, philosophies, and challenges with the aim of achieving mutual understanding with its publics. In the context of higher education institutions like AKSU, effective PR practices are essential for maintaining a positive image, attracting students, and fostering relationships with various stakeholders in higher education institutions like AKSU.

This study aims to address the need to understand how social media influences PR practices at AKSU. As universities increasingly rely on digital platforms for communication, it is crucial to examine the extent to which PR practitioners at AKSU utilise social media, its impact on their communication strategies, and the challenges they face in this digital era.

Research Questions

1. To what extent do PR practitioners at AKSU use social media in discharging their professional duties?
2. What types of social media platforms are most frequently used by PR officers at AKSU?
3. What are the barriers to effective use of social media by PR practitioners at AKSU?

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the multistep flow theory, which evolved from the two-step flow theory proposed by Katz and Lazarsfeld in 1955. The Multistep Flow Theory suggests that the dissemination of information and influence occurs through multiple stages and channels rather than a simple linear process from media to opinion leaders to the general public (Ognyanova, 2017).

The theory proposes that:

1. Information flows through various channels and intermediaries before reaching the final audience.
2. Opinion leaders play a crucial role in interpreting and disseminating information, but they are not the only influencers in the process.
3. Horizontal communication among peers and within social networks is

significant in shaping opinions and behaviours.

4. The flow of information is complex and multidirectional, involving feedback loops and multiple points of influence.

In the context of PR practice at AKSU, the Multistep Flow Theory provides a framework for understanding how information disseminated through social media platforms can reach various stakeholders through multiple channels and influencers within the university community. This theory is particularly relevant in the digital age, where social media platforms facilitate rapid and multidirectional information flow. It helps explain how messages from AKSU's PR department might be interpreted, shared, and reshaped by various actors within the university ecosystem, including students, faculty, staff, and external stakeholders, before reaching their final audience.

Literature Review

In recent years, the integration of social media into public relations practice has received significant scholarly attention. Wright and Hinson (2009) conducted a seminal study on the impact of social media on PR practice, finding that 73% of PR practitioners believed that the emergence of blogs and social media had changed the way their organisations communicate. This study highlighted the transformative potential of social media in PR, setting the stage for further research in this area.

Building on this foundation, Olayinka and Ewuola (2019) examined the impact of social media on PR practice in Nigeria. Their research revealed that social media platforms like instant messaging, social bookmarking, and photo sharing have had a significant impact on how PR practitioners communicate, enabling seamless interactions between organisations and their publics. The study also found that social media has enhanced PR objectives by impacting PR knowledge, improving relationships with stakeholders, and sharing information on the latest innovations in PR tools and methods.

Agba (2017) conducted a higher education study on the influence of social media on PR practices in universities in southeast Nigeria. The research found that social media use has changed traditional methods of information dissemination in universities. However, the study also revealed that the frequency of social media use by PR practitioners was not sufficient, suggesting a gap between the potential and actual use of these platforms in university PR strategies.

Olayinka and Folorunsho (2019) provided further insights into the specific social media platforms used by PR practitioners in Nigeria. Their study found that Facebook and WhatsApp were the most frequently used social media platforms among PR practitioners in Lagos, with 37.8% and 18.9% usage, respectively.

Importantly, 70% of respondents believed that social media greatly enhanced PR departments and personnel performance, underscoring the perceived value of these platforms in PR practice.

The literature also highlights the challenges of effectively using social media for PR. Udomah et al. (2023) noted that while digital technology has transformed PR practice in Nigeria, it also presents challenges, such as the need for continuous monitoring of online exposure and prompt addressing of inaccurate or negative information. This emphasises the dual nature of social media as both an opportunity and a challenge for PR practitioners.

These studies collectively paint a picture of social media as an increasingly important tool in PR practice, particularly in the Nigerian context. However, they also suggest that there is room for improvement in how these platforms are utilised, especially in institutional settings like universities.

Methodology

This study employed a quantitative research design, specifically utilising the survey method. According to Eze (2008), the survey research method enhances the study of both small and large numbers of people derived from the entire population of the study. For this study, the population consisted of 28 staff members from the Information and Communication Technology Unit and the Directorate of Information, Public Relations, and Protocol at Akwa Ibom State University (AKSU).

Given the relatively small size of the population, a census sampling technique was adopted, including all 28 staff members in the study. This approach aligns with Babbie's (1990) view of population as the group about whom we want to draw conclusions. The primary instrument for data collection was a questionnaire designed to gather information on the use of social media in PR practices at AKSU.

The questionnaire was structured in two sections: the first captured demographic information of the respondents, while the second focused on questions related to the research objectives. To ensure validity, the questionnaire was reviewed by experts in testing and measurement, as well as PR professionals, including the researcher's supervisors. The reliability of the instrument was established using the test-retest method, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.72.

Data collection was conducted through face-to-face administration of the questionnaire to all 28 respondents. This method, as noted by Newcomer and Triplett (2010), involves the researcher directly engaging with respondents to collect questionnaire responses. The data collection process spanned two weeks. Quantitative data analysis was performed using descriptive statistics, specifically frequencies and percentages, to address the research questions.

Data Analysis

To address the research questions, we analysed the responses from the survey administered to PR practitioners at Akwa Ibom State University. The following tables present the key findings:

Table 1: Types of social media platforms used by PR officers in AKSU

Option	No of respondents	Percentage
Facebook messenger	3	12
Facebook	12	48
Blog	3	12
WhatsApp	5	20
Instagram	2	8
Total	25	100

Table 1 shows that the majority of respondents (48%) reported using Facebook as their primary social media platform for PR activities. This is followed by WhatsApp (20%), while Facebook Messenger and blogs were used equally (12% each). Instagram was the least used platform among the respondents (8%).

Table 2: Extent of social media influence on PR practice in AKSU

Option	No of respondents	Percentage
Very great extent	6	24
Great extent	10	40
Low extent	5	20
Very low extent	4	16
Total	25	100

Table 2 shows that 40% of respondents believe social media has a significant impact on PR practice at AKSU, while 24% report a very significant influence. However, a notable portion (36%) perceives the influence as low or very low.

Table 3: How the use of social media enhances the achievement of PR objectives in AKSU

Option	No of respondents	Percentage
Helps in shaping attitude of PR practitioner	2	8
Impacting on PR knowledge	1	4
Enhancing relationship with people	5	20
Shaping information on tools and methods of PR	2	8
Enhancing seamless interaction	5	20
All of the above	10	40
Total	25	100

Table 3 reveals that 40% of respondents believe social media enhances PR objectives in multiple ways, including shaping attitudes, impacting knowledge, enhancing relationships, shaping information on tools and methods, and enhancing seamless interaction. Notably, 20% of respondents specifically highlighted the role of social media in enhancing relationships with people and facilitating seamless interaction.

Table 4: Barriers to effective use of social media by PR practitioners in AKSU

Option	No of respondents	Percentage
Bureaucracy in public service	3	12
Issue of poor network	7	28
Insufficient electricity	12	48
Lack of financial support/clear cut policies by government	3	12
Total	25	100

Table 4 identifies the primary barriers to effective social media use in PR practice at AKSU. The most significant barrier reported is insufficient electricity (48%), followed by poor network issues (28%). Bureaucracy in public service and lack of financial support/clear policies were equally cited as barriers (12% each).

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study provide valuable insights into the influence of social media on public relations practice at Akwa Ibom State University (AKSU). The findings reveal a significant adoption of social media platforms by PR practitioners, with Facebook emerging as the dominant platform, followed by WhatsApp and other social media tools. This aligns with the findings of Olayinka and Folorunsho (2019), who reported Facebook and WhatsApp as the most frequently used social media platforms among PR practitioners in Nigeria.

The prevalence of Facebook use in AKSU's PR practice reflects the platform's widespread popularity and its potential for reaching diverse stakeholders. This preference for Facebook can be understood through the lens of the Multistep Flow Theory, which posits that information flows through various channels and intermediaries before reaching the final audience. Facebook's extensive user base and sharing capabilities make it an ideal platform for initiating this multistep flow of information within the university community.

The study reveals that a significant portion of respondents (64%) believe social media has a great or very great extent of influence on PR practice at AKSU. This perception aligns with Wright and Hinson's (2009) findings, which indicated that PR practitioners widely acknowledged the transformative impact of social media on organisational communication. The perceived influence of social media in AKSU's

PR practice suggests that these digital platforms have become integral to the university's communication strategies.

Importantly, the findings highlight the multifaceted benefits of social media in achieving PR objectives. A substantial 40% of respondents agreed that social media enhances PR practice in various ways, including shaping attitudes, impacting knowledge, enhancing relationships, and facilitating seamless interaction. This mirrors the findings of Olayinka and Ewuola (2019), who reported similar benefits of social media in PR practice in Nigeria. The ability of social media to enhance relationships and facilitate interactions is particularly noteworthy, as it exemplifies the horizontal communication and feedback loops emphasised in the Multistep Flow Theory.

However, the study also uncovers significant barriers to the effective use of social media in AKSU's PR practice. The most prominent challenges identified are insufficient electricity (48%), and poor network connectivity (28%). These infrastructure-related issues present unique obstacles in the Nigerian context, potentially limiting the full realisation of social media's potential in PR practice. This finding extends the work of Udomah et al. (2023), who noted challenges in digital PR practice in Nigeria by highlighting specific infrastructure-related barriers.

The identified barriers suggest that while social media offers numerous opportunities for enhancing PR practice, its effectiveness is contingent upon overcoming infrastructural challenges. This nuance is critical when applying the Multistep Flow Theory in developing countries, where technological infrastructure may impede the smooth flow of information through digital channels.

The findings demonstrate that social media significantly influences PR practice at AKSU, offering various benefits while also presenting unique challenges. The preference for platforms like Facebook and the perceived benefits of social media align with both previous research and the principles of the Multistep Flow Theory. However, the infrastructural barriers identified underscore the need for a context-specific approach when implementing social media strategies in PR practice, particularly in settings with similar technological constraints.

Conclusion

This study has investigated the influence of social media on public relations practice at Akwa Ibom State University. The findings reveal that social media, particularly Facebook, plays a significant role in PR activities at AKSU. PR practitioners perceive social media as having a substantial influence on their practice, enhancing their ability to shape attitudes, impact knowledge, and build relationships. However, infrastructural challenges, primarily insufficient electricity and poor network

connectivity, hinder the full potential of social media use in PR practice. The study underscores the relevance of the Multistep Flow Theory in understanding how information disseminates through social media channels within the university community. While social media offers numerous benefits for PR practice at AKSU, addressing the identified barriers is crucial for maximising its effectiveness. Overall, this research contributes to an understanding of social media's role in PR practice within the context of a Nigerian university.

Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. AKSU should invest in alternative power sources and improved internet infrastructure to mitigate the barriers of insufficient electricity and poor network connectivity, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of social media use in PR practice.
2. The university should develop a comprehensive social media strategy that leverages the popularity of Facebook while also exploring other platforms to diversify their PR outreach and engage with different stakeholder groups.
3. PR practitioners at AKSU should receive regular training on emerging social media trends and best practices to maximise the benefits of these platforms in achieving PR objectives and fostering stakeholder relationships.

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